

REPORT OF SOME BASIC L-AMINO-ACID OXIDASES PEPTIDES ISOLATED FROM THE NEOTROPICAL LANSBERG'S HOGNOSE VIPER (*Porthidium lansbergii hutmanni*) SNAKE VENOM FROM MARGARITA ISLAND (VENEZUELA)

REPORTE DE ALGUNOS PÉPTIDOS DE L-AMINOÁCIDO OXIDASAS AISLADAS DEL VENENO DE LA SERPIENTE NEOTROPICAL DE LANSBERG (*Porthidium lansbergii hutmanni*) DE LA ISLA DE MARGARITA (VENEZUELA)

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ABSTRACT

L-amino acid oxidases (SV-LAAOs, EC 1.4.3.2) are flavo-enzymes that catalyse the stereo specific oxidative transamination of L-amino acids to α -keto acids with production of ammonia and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). These enzymes are widely distributed in many different organisms, including snakes from the Elapidae, Viperidae and Crotalidae families, and present as the major component of many of their venoms. The Lansberg's hognose viper (*Porthidium lansbergii hutmanni*) (*Plh*) venom characterization and purification included an arrangement of SDS-PAGE and 2D electrophoresis, MALDI TOF/TOF and tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). In this work, 8 peptides from SV-LAAOs from *Plh* snakes were named as PLH1-LAAO, PLH2-LAAO, PLH3-LAAO, PLH4-LAAO, PLH5-LAAO, PLH6-LAAO, PLH7-LAAO and PLH8-LAAO. This paper summarises the physico-chemical properties and structural characteristics of various SV-LAAOs peptides from *Plh* snake venom.

KEY WORDS: Lethality, MALDI-TOF/TOF, proteomic, LC-MS/MS, venom, Serpentes, Viperidae.

RESUMEN

Las L-amino ácidos oxidasas (SV-LAAOs, EC 1.4.3.2) son flavo-enzimas que catalizan la transaminación estereoespecífica oxidativa de los L-amino ácidos hacia los α -ketoácidos, con producción de amonio y peróxido de hidrógeno (H_2O_2). Estas enzimas están ampliamente distribuidas en muchos organismos, incluyendo las serpientes de las familias Elapidae, Viperidae y Crotalidae, a través de los mayores componentes de sus venenos. La caracterización y purificación del veneno de la serpiente de Lansberg's (*Porthidium lansbergii hutmanni*) (*Plh*) incluyó un proceso de electroforesis simple (SDS-PAGE) y de dos dimensiones, así como un análisis por MALDI TOF/TOF y espectrometría "tándem" de masas (LC-MS/MS). En este trabajo, se describen 8 péptidos de SV-LAAOs en el veneno de *Plh* denominadas como PLH1-LAAO, PLH2-LAAO, PLH3-LAAO, PLH4-LAAO, PLH5-LAAO, PLH6-LAAO, PLH7-LAAO y PLH8-LAAO. Este trabajo resume las propiedades fisicoquímicas y características estructurales de dichos péptidos hallados en diversas SV-LAAOs del veneno de la serpiente *Plh*.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Letalidad, MALDI-TOF/TOF, proteómica, LC-MS/MS, veneno, Serpentes, Viperidae.

INTRODUCTION

Lansberg's hognose viper (*Porthidium lansbergii hutmanni*) (*Plh*) snake bite is a described medical condition in the Macanao peninsula of Margarita Island (Nueva Esparta state, Venezuela) (Girón *et al.* 2011, De Sousa *et al.* 2013). The *Plh* venom under experimental conditions produces oedema, necrosis, bleeding (skin bruising, gastrointestinal haemorrhage and haematuria) and lymphatic vessel damage, with degradation of extracellular matrix effects (Pineda *et al.* 2008, Girón *et al.* 2011). The occurrence of *Plh* snakebite has been incompletely reviewed, and the basic

pathogenic mechanism of this envenomation persists as an open question.

Among the described toxins in this snake venom there were the L-amino acid oxidases (SV-LAAOs, EC 1.4.3.2). The pharmacological and biological effects of LAAOs include action on platelets, induction of apoptosis, haemorrhagic effects, and cytotoxicity (Izidoro *et al.* 2006).

Exploring by proteomics methods the *Plh* venom would be very useful to find the snakebite-related biomarkers, which will permit the description of the physio-pathological mechanism of this accident. Recent findings in mass

spectrometry has become a methodology that answers many analytical questions, trying to dichotomise the molecular complexity of proteins (Breker *et al.* 2014), that would allow the measurement of isolated molecules of SV-LAAOs.

In a previous paper (Pineda *et al.* 2019a), a proteome and mass spectrometry study of *Plh* venom showed an ample spectre of different proteins, including SV-LAAOs. In the current work we are better describing SV-LAAOs peptides by means of SDS-PAGE and 2 dimensions (2D) electrophoresis, MALDI/TOF/TOF and tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) in this venom.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents

Working solutions: reagents of high purity $\geq 98\%$ were purchased from Merck and Riedel de Haen, Germany. Electrophoresis: Reagents (BIO-RAD, USA), IPG Strips pH 3-10, 11 cm (BIO-RAD, USA); casein (Merck and Riedel de Haen, Germany); Immunoblotting: Equine peroxidase-coupled-equine IgG antibody (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, CA, USA), Nitrocellulose membrane (BIO-RAD, USA), Super Signal West Pico® chemi-luminescence development kit (Thermo Scientific, USA); MALDI-TOF/TOF: α -Cyano-4-hydroxycinnamic acid matrix (α -CHCA) (SIGMA, Mo, USA), Acetonitrile, Trifluoroacetic Acid and diethyl ether (SIGMA, Mo, USA); LC-MS/MS: OFFGEL Room Temp High Res® Kit (Agilent Technologies, USA), IEF pH 3-10 24 centimetres (cm) strips (GE Healthcare, USA), Swine Trypsin (PROMEGA), Electro spray calibrate solution 63606 and Calibration Tune Mix ESI (SIGMA-Fluka, USA).

Software

For the statistical studies, the Prism® program (Graph Pad, Software) (Ying-Ming *et al.* 2014) was employed; for the one dimension gels analysis Quantity One® (BIO-RAD, USA) software was used; while for the two-dimensional gels electrophoresis analysis, the PD Quest® program (BIO-RAD) was utilised (Serrano *et al.* 2005).

In the MALDI TOF/TOF mass spectrometry analysis. Compass 1.2 SR1 for Flex Analysis (Bruker Daltonics) was the software employed. The LC-MS/MS analyses the Compass 1.2 SR1 program for Microtof/Maxis® (Bruker-Daltonics) was utilised (Chernushevich *et al.* 2001).

Venom

Porthidium lansbergii hutmanni (*Plh*) venom was obtained by manual milking of 6 female and male adult specimens. This subspecies is endemic to Margarita Island predominating in Porlamar, Bahía de Juan Griego, Pampatar, Macanao and Coche Island (Nueva Esparta state, Venezuela). The animals were captured in Macanao peninsula, geographically located at Longitude: "O64°16'59.99" and Latitude: "N11°1'0.01" (Fig. 1).

All snakes were housed at the Research Laboratory Serpentarium, Faculty of Pharmacy of the Universidad Central de Venezuela. The snakes were milked upon reaching the Serpentarium, after their adaptation for a week (w). The venom, once obtained, was crystalised under vacuum in a desiccator containing CaCl_2 as a desiccant, and preserved at 4°C (Frigidaire FGVU21F8QF Vertical Freezer, USA), until its later use.

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of *Porthidium lansbergii hutmanni* at Macanao Peninsula of Margarita Island (Venezuela) (in black).

Ethical statement

Qualified staff prepared all the experimental methods relating to the use of live animals. Applicable regulations as well as institutional guidelines, agreeing to protocols approved by the Institute of Anatomy of the Universidad Central de Venezuela Ethical Committee (project # 260319), following the norms obtained from the guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals, published by the US National Institute of Health (NIH 1985).

Proteomic characterisation of the *Plh* venom

SDS-PAGE analysis

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (12%) under reducing conditions; 5 µg of protein total loaded per well was done (Laemmli 1970), using a Mini-Protean II system (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Hercules, CA). Each experiment was performed in duplicate.

Two-dimensional (2D) electrophoresis of *Plh* venom

The proteomic map was carried out using two-dimensional (2D) electrophoresis of the *Plh* venom. The analysis of the venom was run twice obtaining two gels per sample. Briefly, 100 µg of *Plh* venom was dissolved in 50 µL of protease inhibitors cocktail (4-(2-aminoethyl)-benzene-sulphonyl fluoride (AEBSF), E-64, bestatin, leupeptin, aprotinin and disodium EDTA). Then, 150 µL of 8M Urea, 2M Thiourea, 4% CHAPS, 20 mM DTT and 0.5% v/v of a commercial ampholyte mixture were supplemented for equilibration. The resultant mixture was located on a commercial non-linear immobilised wide range (pH 3-10) gradient (IPG) strip for isoelectric focusing in the first dimension. The IPG strip were then repositioned at the top of the 12.5% SDS second-dimensional gel. It was detached from the unstained gel, and incubated in SDS sample buffer containing 3% β-mercaptoethanol for 30 min. The achieved gels were coloured with Blue Silver (Candiano *et al.* 2015). Later were digitised by densitometry, and the resultant images were analysed estimating their isoelectric point, and the molecular masses of the envisaged spots. The variances between the intensity of the spots were not assessed due the analysis was carried out from a qualitative perspective only. After electrophoresis was run, are

levant lane suspected for its molecular mass to be an SV-LAAOs (>90 kDa), in correspondence with formerly characterised venoms from species within this genus (Mackessy 2009, Pineda *et al.* 2019a).

Proteomic analysis by Matrix-Assisted Laser (MALDI TOF TOF) of *Plh* venom

The venom proteins were run in a 10% SDS-PAGE electrophoresis under reducing conditions for the *Plh* venom analysis by mass spectrometry (MS) (Griffiths *et al.* 2018). At that moment the gel was coloured with Coomassie blue staining. Once the bands were visualised, small portions were cut and each of these fragments was destained with 30% acetonitrile (ACN) and 250 mM ammonium bicarbonate. Afterward they were dehydrated with aqueous solution at 90% of ACN and subsequent digestion of proteins incubating the gel fragments at 37°C for 18 h, coating them with a solution of 12.5 ng/µL trypsin in 50 mM ammonium bicarbonate. The triptich peptides obtained were concentrated and purified by using ZIP-TIP C18® tips, using an aqueous solution containing 60% ACN and 1% formic acid as eluent. The samples ionisation necessary for the mass spectrometry analysis was performed by MALDI (Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization). Each sample was mixed in a 2: 1 ratio with a suspension of α-Cyano-4-hydroxycinnamic acid (α-CHCA), formulated in 50% ACN and 0.05% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and allowed to dry over a MALDI plate, at room temperature until their complete crystallisation.

The analysis by mass spectrometry was accomplished on a spectrometer equipped with a TOF/TOF (Time-Of-Flight/Time-Of-Flight) type analyser, operated in a reflectron mode. The peptides MS/MS analysis that generated the most intense signal was carried out using the MASCOT program (MS/MS Ion Search®, Matrix Science) with the following parameters: Taxonomy: All Entries, Variable modifications: oxidation (M), deamidated (NQ), Fixed Modifications: propionamited (C); against the database of the NCBI (National Center for Biotechnology Information, USA). Additionally, the peptide alignment sequences acquired through the manual interpretation of the spectra was achieved, with non-redundant sequences through the BLAST® program (NCBI), considered as useable, the values of the mass/charge ratio of each peptide (m/z).

Proteomic analysis by liquid chromatography coupled to Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) of *Plh* venom

For more proteomic evidence the peptide alignment sequences were run in a liquid chromatography, coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS). Briefly, 100 µg/100 µL of venom peptide was incubated for 15 min with 5 mM DTT and subsequently for another 15 min with 10 mM iodoacetamide. Later, the sample was incubated at 37°C with trypsin in a 1:40 ratio enzyme: substrate. The achieved sample composed of a mixture of tripeptide peptides, was placed in a fractionator (3100 OFFGEL Fractionator, Agilent, USA), for the fractionation of these peptides according to their isoelectric point. The products acquired were recovered in 24 liquid phase fractions of 150 µL each. A linear fixed gradient strip of pH 3-10 of 24 cm was employed. Throughout the process, a voltage/hour ratio of 50 kV/h was reached at a 4500 V. Current: 50 µA and Power: 200 mW. At that point, the fractions obtained were injected into a high performance chromatographic system, equipped with a C18 reverse phase pre-column (5 µm and 2 cm in length) and a C18 chromatographic column (5 µm and 10 cm in length). A linear gradient was created between a solution Phase A: composed of 0.1% formic acid in deionised water and a solution Phase B: composed of 0.1% formic acid in ACN. This gradient was progressively established from 0% from Phase B to 80% from Phase B in 60 min. Every eluate continued through an interface coupled to a tandem mass analyser (MS/MS) time of flight-quadrupole. The ionisation of the peptides was carried out by ESI (Electrospray ionisation) with voltage in the capillary of -4500V, Gas flow desolvation: 2 L/min, Gas nebuliser: 5.8 psi and temperature: 160°C. The mass range analysed was 50-3000 Da/z. Calibration was done using a commercial calibrator solution. The analysis and searches of the obtained monoisotopic masses for the peptide fragments were carried out according to MALDI TOF/TOF.

Statistical analysis

The differences between experimental groups was made using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), using as a statistical test, the Dunnett test considered as significant those results with an error probability $P < 0.01$. Analysis was finished using SPSS version 2.0.

RESULTS

SDS-PAGE analysis

The SDS-PAGE of *Plh* crude venom displayed two venom bands (~120 and 130kDa) at locations in which the high molecular mass of L-amino acid oxidases (LAAOs) are frequently described (Mackessy 2009) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. SDS-PAGE of *Plh* under reducing conditions for MALDI/TOF-TOF. The arrows point toward the cut bands for analysis by MALDI/TOF-TOF. (A) Molecular mass markers. (B) *Plh* venom: SV-LAAOs (arrows).

Two-dimensional (2D) electrophoresis of *Plh* venom

When *Plh* venom was run on 2DE gels, ~101 spots were found (Pineda *et al.* 2019a). Two spots (~120 kDa) were recovered for the mass spectrometry analysis. Both proteins showed isoelectric points with values around 7.8 ranges (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Two-dimensional (2D) electrophoresis of *Plh* venom (Pineda *et al.* 2019). Two spots (~ 120.0 kDa) taken for the amino-acids SV-LAOOs sequences study (circle). (A) *Plh* venom. (B) molecular mass markers. Two hundred micrograms were run on an isoelectric focusing (IEF) (pH 3 to 10) and 12.5% SDS-PAGE (m/v), obtained by Coomassie blue staining. kDa: molecular masses; SV-LAOOS: Snake venom L-amino acid oxidases.

Identification of the SV-LAOOs-venom proteins by mass spectrometry MALDI/TOF-TOF

Table 1 shows the peptide alignment sequences obtained with non-redundant sequences deposited in public databases through the BLAST® program (NCBI).

Proteomic analysis by liquid chromatography coupled to Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) of *Plh* venom

Table 1 also synthesises the results achieved from SV-LAOOs-venom by analysis by liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) with non-redundant sequences deposited in public databases through the BLAST® program (NCBI). Throughout the analysis was possible to identify proteins corresponding to different L-amino acid oxidases from two isoforms. SV-LAOOs peptides from *Plh* snake venom were designed as PLH1-LAAO, PLH2-LAAO, PLH3-LAAO, PLH4-LAAO, PLH5-LAAO, PLH6-LAAO, PLH7-LAAO and PLH8-LAAO.

Multiple sequence alignment

The specific locations of peptides within the protein sequence is showed in Fig. 4.

Table 1. Identification of the *Plh* venom SV-LAOOS by MALDI/TOF-TOF (MTT) and LC-MS/MS (LMSMS) mass spectrometry.

Bands	Peptides name	Identified sequence peptide	Identified Protein	Taxonomy	Score BLAST	% sequence
~120/130 kDa	PLH1-LAAO.	R.ETDYEEFLEIAR.N	L-aminoacid oxidase (MTT)	<i>Protobothrops flavoviridis</i> <i>Bothrops jararaca</i>	50.3	100
~120/130 kDa	PLH2-LAAO	R.NDEEGWYANLGPMR.L	L-aminoacid oxidase (MTT)	<i>Protobothrops stejnegeri</i>	58.3	100
~120/130 kDa	PLH3-LAAO	K.DCADIVINDLSLIHQPK.E	L-aminoacid oxidase (LMSMS)	<i>Sistrurus catenatus edwardsi</i>	68.1	100
~120/130 kDa	PLH4-LAAO	R.NDEEGWYANLGPMR.L	L-aminoacid oxidase (LMSMS)	<i>Protobothrops stejnegeri</i>	51.0	100
~120/130 kDa	PLH5-LAAO	R.NDKEGWYANLGPMR.L	L-aminoacid oxidase (LMSMS)	<i>Gloydus blomhoffii</i> <i>Lachesis muta</i>	57.9	100
~120/130 kDa	PLH6-LAAO	K.DCGDIVINDLSLIHQPK.E	L-aminoacid oxidase (LMSMS)	<i>Bothropoides pauloensis</i>	68.1	100
~120/130 kDa	PLH7-LAAO	K.SAGQLYEESLGK.V	L-aminoacid oxidase (LMSMS)	<i>Calloselasma rhodostoma</i> <i>Gloydus blomhoffii</i> <i>Gloydus halys</i>	45.2	100
~120/130 kDa	PLH8-LAAO	K.SAGQLYQESLGK.A	L-aminoacid oxidase (LMSMS)	<i>Daboia russellii russellii</i>	44.8	100

PLH2	-----RNDEEGWYANLGPML-----	16
PLH4	-----RNDEEGWYANLGPML-----	16
PLH5	-----RNDKEGWYANLGPML-----	16
PLH6	-----	0
PLH3	-----	0
<i>Crotalus</i>		
SCADDRNPLEECFRETIDYEEFLEIARNGLTIVT SNPKHVVIV GAGMAGLSAAYVLAGAGHQVTVLEASERVGGRRVRTYRKKD		
WYANLGPMLPTKHRIVREYIRKFGQLN 110		
PLH1	-----RETIDYEEFLEIARN-----	14
PLH7	-----	0
PLH8	-----	0
PLH2	-----	16
PLH4	-----	16
PLH5	-----	16
PLH6	-----	0
PLH3	-----	0
<i>Crotalus</i>		
EFFQENENAWYFIKNIRKRVREVKNNPGILEYVPVKPSEEGKSAQAQLYVESLRKVV KELKRTNCKYILDKYDTYSTKEYLLKE		
GNLSPGAVDMIGDLLNEDSGYVVSFIES 220		
PLH1	-----	14
PLH7	-----KSAGQLYEESLGKV-----	14
PLH8	-----KSAGQLYQESLGKA-----	14
PLH2	-----	16
PLH4	-----	16
PLH5	-----	16
PLH6	-----	0
PLH3	-----	0
<i>Crotalus</i>		
LKHDDIFGYEKRFDEIVGGMDQLPTSMYEAIKEKVQVHFNARVIEIQNDRETKVTYQTSANEMPSVTADYVIVCTTSRAAR		
RIKFEPPLPPKKAHALRSVHYRS GTKIF 330		
PLH1	-----	14
PLH7	-----	14
PLH8	-----	14
PLH2	-----	16
PLH4	-----	16
PLH5	-----	16
PLH6	-----KDCGDIVINDLSLIHQLPKE-----	20
PLH3	-----KDCADIVINDLSLIHQLPKE-----	20
<i>Crotalus</i>		
LTCKRKFWEEDGIRGGKSTTDLPSRFIYPNHNF TSGVGVIIAYGIGDDANFFQALDFKDCADIVINDLSLIHQLPKEDIQTF CR		
PSMIQRWVSLDKYAMGGITTFPTY QF 440		
PLH1	-----	14
PLH7	-----	14
PLH8	-----	14
PLH2	-----	16
PLH4	-----	16
PLH5	-----	16
PLH6	-----	20
PLH3	-----	20
<i>Crotalus</i>		
QHFSEALTAPFKRIYFAGEYTAQFHGWIDSTIKSGLTAARDVNRASENPSGIHLSNDN-- 498		
PLH1	-----	14
PLH7	-----	14
PLH8	-----	14

Figure 4. The previous alignment shows the positioning of each of the identified fragments on a homologous LAAOs. It can be observed that there are 2 redundant fragments (PLH2 = PLH4). It is important to highlight that the small differences between some aligned fragments in the same region correspond to different LAAOs subunits. In summary, they are seven fragments identified from two or more isoforms.

DISCUSSION

Practically whole LAAOs currently expressed are flavo-proteins of dimeric structure, where each

subunit exhibits a non-covalent bond with flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD) commonly found in snake venom SV-LAAOs. Flavins from SV-LAAOs produces the typical yellow colour of most of the

snake venoms and influence their toxicity since causes an oxidative stress produced by the hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) (Guo *et al.* 2012). As formerly established, the enzyme catalyses the oxidative deamination of the basic amino acids: L-histidine, L-ornithine, L-arginine and L-lysine (Sun *et al.* 2010).

In the conformation of same snake venom can concur, acidic, neutral and basic forms of SV-LAAOs showing among them diverse pharmacological activities (Stiles *et al.* 1991). They have been described as homodimers and monomers, which present in their natural form molecular masses fluctuating between 120 to 150 kDa, and 50 to 70 kDa in their corresponding forms (Du & Clemetson 2002). The subunits of LAAOs may keep up as one either covalently or non-covalently. Agreeing to 2D gel information, both LAAOs subunits of *Plh* may be covalently link. The samples preparation for isoelectric focusing assay were conditions that allow non-covalently linked subunits separating. Moreover, the reducing conditions employed, adequate to propose a possible covalent link between subunits.

The SV-LAAOs represent the main component of many snake venoms, which produces different organic impacts, such as oedema, haemolysis, haemorrhage, induction and/or inhibition of platelet aggregation, induction of apoptosis, cytotoxicity, among other activities (Costa *et al.* 2014). Most of these activities induced by LAAOs are in part explained by the generation of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), a reactive oxygen (RO) species that collects on the surface of cell membranes. It is also generally known that escalating RO concentrations, it stimulates mitochondrial imbalances that origin cellular death (Du & Clemetson 2002).

Recently, Lu *et al.* (2018) described a 65 kDa glycoprotein BM-Apotxin, an SV-LAAOs with high sequence identity to other snake venom LAAOs, which can selectively destroy tumour cells, with minus cytotoxicity to the normal cells; its anti-tumour action is primarily due to the H_2O_2 produced from SV-LAAOs oxidation. In the other hand, the central actions on haemostasis by SV-LAAOs occurs on platelet aggregation. Nonetheless, the activity versions are differing, whereas, for LAAOs obtained from the *Bothrops moojeni*, *Bothrops alternatus*, *Bothrops atrox*, *Trimeresurus musquamatus*, *Crotalus durissus cascavella* venoms are able to induce platelet aggregation; for SV-LAAOs obtained from *Vipera berus*, *Vipera lebetina*, *Agkistrodon blomhoffi*, *Agkistrodon halys*,

Naja naja oxiana and *Naja naja kaouthia* venoms, the reverse result as inhibition of platelet aggregation mediated by ADP or collagen was observed (Guo *et al.* 2012).

In this work, 8 peptides from SV-LAAOs (from *Plh* snakes) were also designed as PLH1-LAAO, PLH2-LAAO, PLH3-LAAO, PLH4-LAAO, PLH5-LAAO, PLH6-LAAO, PLH7-LAAO and PLH8-LAAO, respectively. Each predicted peptide precursors comprised from 14 to 20 amino acid residues and shared a level (from 44.8 to 68.1%) of sequence identity with other SV-LAAOs already described (Table 1). These sequence identity percentages are clearly high since it is a local and not a global alignment. Furthermore, by making multiple sequence alignments available from SV-LAAOs, the identity percentages were above 70%. Remarkably, the sequence identities among these SV-LAAOs were extremely high. Authors, such as Jin *et al.* (2007) proposed that the identities among some continental elapid SV-LAAOs and Australian elapid LAAOs, are superior than 85%. On the other hand, the identities between elapid SV-LAAOs and Viperidae LAAOs are also over 75%. These data suggested that SV-LAAOs found in the current work (Viperidae venom) are related, regarding the amino acid sequences, to diverse SV-LAAOs.

On the topic of the eight fragments reported: Fragment 1 (from MALDI analysis) corresponds to the most N-terminal region from some isoforms enzyme between amino acids 11 and 22 approximately. The fragment two and four are same and corresponding to N-terminal of subunits between the aminoacidic positions 74 and 90 (the fragment five correspond this position). During the MALDI analysis, the molecular weights of the two proteins analysed corresponding to the two spots from 2D gel had to be obtain. The difference between fragments 2, 4 regarding fragment 5, is just a glutamic acid, modified by a lysine, suggesting the possible need for a polar amino acid at that position. As mentioned before, these fragments 2 and 4 are from the same protein, while 5 corresponds to the other isoform of the enzyme, possibly. The latter is also applicable for fragments 7 and 8 that differ by exchanging glutamic acid for glutamine (structurally similar) and an alanine by a valine which maintain hydrophobic characteristics. Both fragments may correspond to the mid region of the protein between positions 153 and 167 of its isoforms. The largest fragments identified (20 amino acids in length), correspond to C-terminal region between positions 390 and 410. The exchanging of a glycine by alanine suggests they

could also correspond to two different isoforms. In summary, 7 fragments of the two SV-LAAOs isoforms were identified.

Finally, in the literature there is only one publication of ophidic accident by *Plh* snakes in Nueva Esparta state (Venezuela) (Cornejo-Escobar *et al.* 2013), with local symptoms that involved sudden pain and local bite bleeding, as well as oedema, erythema and burnt sensation, for which specific clinical information is lacking. Experimentally we have found that the *Plh* venom induced haemorrhagic, myotoxic, anticoagulant, fibrinolytic, fibrinogenolytic and phospholipase A₂ activities in mice (Girón *et al.* 2011, Pineda *et al.* 2019b). When these findings are associated with the activities that have been described for the SV-LAAOs, we think that several clinical signs observed in the envenomed victims must be due to the action of the SV-LAAOs, in which haemostatic activities, such as interactions with platelets (activating aggregation or inhibition) and induction of haemorrhages and apoptosis (Suhr & Kim 1999), inducing haemolysis and oedema (Ali *et al.* 2000), cytotoxicity (Hiu & Yap 2020) have been described.

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